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**Affective-Discursive Ecologies of the Far Right: Multimodal Softening, Mobilisation,
and Algorithmic Proximity on Instagram**

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Abstract

This article examines how far-right communication on Instagram uses positively-valenced affect and humour to normalise extremist worldviews. Drawing on research on mainstreaming, memetic communication, and affective publics, it conceptualises far-right Instagram as an affective-discursive ecology where ideology, emotion, and platform logics intersect. Through algorithmic ethnography and multimodal discourse analysis, the study analyses 2,603 Reels featuring far-right adjacent themes.

The analysis identifies three overlapping modalities: (1) humorous, ironic, and meta-reflexive content, framing extremity as playful or self-aware; (2) wholesome and nostalgic aestheticisation that softens exclusionary messaging through sentimental imagery; and (3) inspirational, glorifying, and aspirational aestheticisation, casting ideological commitment as awakening or heroic civilisational defence. Algorithmic clustering further politicises ostensibly non-political material, allowing neutral or unrelated posts to reinforce far-right narratives through contextual adjacency.

The study argues that effective responses must address these emotional, aesthetic, and infrastructural conditions.

Keywords: algorithmic ethnography, multimodal discourse analysis, far right, political communication, propaganda, affective economy, social media

Introduction: Affective Strategies, Memetic Communication, and Platform Amplification

Digital Media and the Contemporary Far Right

Contemporary social media environments have become key sites of political acculturation for youth. Studies show that social media has surpassed traditional news as their primary source of political information (European Parliament, 2023; Newman, 2023) and that these platforms enhance the organisational reach of far-right projects such as the AfD (Frindte, 2025). Analyses of online media ecosystems highlight a predominance of right-leaning content (Media Matters, 2023), aligning with broader trends of young men increasingly expressing openness to far-right ideas (Abou-Chadi, 2024). The term *far right* is used as an umbrella concept following Pirro (2023) to denote a heterogeneous field of actors and communicative practices broadly united by nativist, authoritarian, and anti-egalitarian worldviews. In the context of social media, the far right is approached as a discursive and aesthetic space, identified through recurring thematic, stylistic, and affective repertoires rather than formal affiliation. Within networked spaces, far-right publics function as affective communities that produce resonance, humour, and peer recognition (Collins, 2024), often in contexts marked by social alienation and weakened community infrastructures (Humphrey & Bliuc, 2022;

Wilson, 2018). This constellation underscores the need to examine not only the ideological dimensions of far-right communication but also the affective and infrastructural dynamics shaping its circulation and appeal.

To situate this analysis, the following section outlines the conceptual frameworks that inform the study, focusing on research on mainstreaming, memetic communication, multimodality, and affect in far-right digital cultures.

Far-right communicators employ affective strategies that mask extremist messages beneath humour, wholesomeness, and other positively valenced expression. These modes help make extremist discourse more broadly accepted and shareable, supporting circulation across digital platforms. Such practices align with Rothut et al.'s (2024) conception of mainstreaming as a dual process involving *content positioning*, the insertion of radical ideas into wider discourse, and *susceptibility*, the attunement of ideas to audience emotions and dispositions. They outline a taxonomy that operationalises this process, including tactics like dog-whistling, calculated provocation, exploiting platform affordances, affectively softened forms of communication, among others. Such mechanisms translate extremist messages into relatable, entertaining forms, resonating with broader accounts of *metapolitical* persuasion and the cultural diffusion of far-right ideas (Miller-Idriss, 2020, Nangle, 2017, Woods & Hahner, 2020). On social media mainstreaming is facilitated through rhetorical softening, platform-specific affordances, audio-visual editing styles, algorithmic ranking, and other aspects.

Multimodal Memes as Mainstreaming Devices

A central feature of far-right online communication is meme use, which is critical for understanding how humour and affect operate in the propagation of extremist messages (e.g., DeVries, Bessant, & Watts, 2021; Nangle, 2017; Woods & Hahner, 2020). Following Shifman's (2013) definition, internet memes are digital items that share common content, form, or stance; are created with mutual awareness of one another; and are circulated, imitated, and transformed by users across digital networks. On short-form video platforms memes operate as template-based performances, built from recurring combinations of gesture, soundtrack, editing conventions, and caption. Platform affordances encode imitation and reenactment directly into the infrastructure of memetic production (Grzenkiewicz & Wildfeuer, 2025, Han, 2024). Through these multimodal, participatory processes, ideological and affective messages circulate via humour, aesthetic pleasure, and playful collaboration, obfuscating entertainment and political expression. meme production fosters in-group identification and the creation of online environments conducive to 'radicalisation' (Keenan, 2020).

Bolt Rasmussen (2021) describes late capitalist society as held together less by shared values or institutional cohesion than by fragmented images, corporate symbols, and a "complex convergence of media-induced mass affect" (pp. 67–69). This fractured, hyper-mediated landscape renders memetic communication especially potent, particularly for far-right ideological messaging. Concise, information-dense, and participatively constructed, memes are cognitively easy to process, produce, and circulate, traits well-suited to an era of acceleration, overload, and socio-political instability (Eriksen, 2016). Networked individuals

navigating relentless information flows and shifting digital trends encounter ideal conditions for emotionally charged, visually simple messages to gain traction. Far-right actors capitalise on these dynamics, recognising that political influence increasingly bypasses rational deliberation and instead hinges on transgression, the mobilisation of diffuse resentments, and the recoding of latent hatreds into seductive, pop-cultural forms (Bolt Rasmussen, 2021). Memes' apparent simplicity thus conceals their power to encode layered messages, obscure extremity, and circulate widely, even beyond users' explicit political identifications.

Far-right communicators employ memetic *détournement*, appropriating and repurposing pop-cultural symbols to embed engaging ideological subtexts (Woods & Hahner, 2020). Rather than conveying explicit extremist messages, much of this content uses ironic playfulness to broaden boundaries of public acceptability and 'shift the Overton window' (McSwiney & Sengul, 2024). In this sense, memes operate as mechanisms of acculturation and normalisation, adaptive, dynamic forms of cultural production attuned to the aesthetics and emotional economies of digital life.

On contemporary platforms, memetic communication takes on a distinctly multimodal character, engendering potent immersive experiences of consumption and participation. Following Kress (2010), *multimodality* refers to meaning produced through the interaction of multiple semiotic modes; image, writing, sound, etc, possessing distinct communicative affordances. Meaning emerges through the orchestration of distinct elements. This study treats far-right communication as multimodal discourse, in which ideological cues are embedded in aesthetic, sonic, and embodied patterns. Recent research on TikTok has highlighted processes of multimodal rhythm and embodied meaning-making (Han, 2024) and

developed annotation frameworks for analysing short-form audiovisual design (Grzenkowicz & Wildfeuer, 2025). Earlier visual-social-media studies on Instagram demonstrate how composition, color, and gaze operate as visual-semiotic resources, signalling identity and affect (e.g., Pauwels, 2019). Hakoköngäs et al. (2020) show that far-right groups employ multimodal meme strategies to construct nationalistic narratives and demonise outgroups, while Schmid, Schulze, & Drexel, (2024) demonstrate that the combination of humour and extremist rhetoric significantly boosts the viral reach of content, aiding in the mainstreaming of far-right ideas. This context justifies a qualitative multimodal content-analytic approach, enabling systematic examination of how ideological and affective meanings are co-produced across visual, textual, and sonic layers in far-right Reels.

Soft Affective Strategies in Far-Right Digital Culture

Research on far-right communication increasingly examines the role of positive or “soft” affects in sustaining ideological appeal. Far-right content frequently deploys framings like nostalgia and pride to lend emotional resonance to exclusionary worldviews. Frischlich (2021) identifies a form of eudaimonic entertainment in which extremist producers appeal to meaning, and collective purpose, rather than only aggression or outrage, emotionally-charging narratives that can function as calls to violent action. While often linked to prosocial outcomes, eudaimonic experiences can equally be appropriated within extremist propaganda to cultivate devotion, morally framing justification for violence. Albertazzi and Bonansinga (2024) demonstrate how radical-right actors on TikTok mobilise pride, hope, and aspiration to position their movements as empowering and relatable, aligning ideological communication with familiar social-media genres of self-improvement and positivity.

Such affective framings extend beyond persuasion to constitute *affective publics* (Papacharissi, 2015), networked formations bound by shared moods and sensations rather than rational agreement. In the context of short-form video, these publics are built through affective cues. For instance, nostalgia might operate through idealised historical footage, pride through national symbols and colonial glorification; and “wholesomeness” through nature imagery. These forms encourage identification, making messages resonant or comforting, whilst their varied layering likely reduces audience fatigue that may eventually result from negatively-emotive content.

As Devries et al, (2021) argue, far-right discourse often hinges on exchanges of love, trust, and “likeness,” cultivating affiliation with idealised, racialised constructs such as “the white race,” the nuclear family, the nation or other strategically leveraged ‘meta communities’ (Lamour, 2020). These affective formations are structured by exclusion: love for the in-group is articulated through the portrayal of out-groups as threats to the cherished object of affection (Devries et al., 2021). Pichel-Vázquez and Enguix Grau (2021) similarly show how emotions like joy and belonging are instrumentalised to produce intimate, protective attachments to imagined communities. In work by Berntzen (2020) far-right communication framed around positive emotions generated significantly higher engagement on social media than posts invoking fear or hate.

Using ‘wholesome’ or ‘cute’ aesthetics enhances reach and emotional resonance while evading moderation. These soft affective cues mask ideology, facilitating narrative circulation. For instance, Tebaldi and Plum (2024) show how far-right narratives on “folkish instagram” are reframed through aestheticised content and euphemistic language like “white

positivity,” constructing appealing identities that present exclusionary beliefs as self-improvement and cultural pride. This strategy incorporates traditional gender roles, myth, and beauty to align white supremacy with familiar lifestyle imagery. Leidig (2023) demonstrates how maternal and lifestyle content normalises nativist gender roles and xenophobia, while Argentino’s (2021) analysis of “Pastel QAnon” reveals how soft visual cultures draw women and younger users into conspiratorial milieus. Darwish (2024) analyses eco-fascist messaging, revealing how affective, optimistic imagery conceals exclusionary agendas.

Humour and irony intersect with these affects to broaden engagement. Research shows that far-right content blending humour with extreme messaging circulates more widely than material without humour (Schmid et al., 2024), with memes functioning as a repertoire of inside jokes. This dynamic rests on the communal role of humour: as Greene and Day (2019) note, shared satire fosters belonging, reinforcing cohesion through perceived exclusivity, an effect likely especially potent for socially isolated or disaffected individuals (Pfundmair et al., 2022), who may gain social esteem from countercultural or rebellious in-group identities. Nagle (2017) further argues that far-right culture draws on online spaces of “transgressive pranksterism,” where irony and offensive humour obscure ideology, offering plausible deniability while casting mainstream values as naïve or conformist and thereby redefining cultural normativity.

The architecture of digital communication platforms plays a central role in facilitating the dissemination and normalisation of ideological material. Anonymity and pseudonymity lower barriers to participation while shielding users from accountability, enabling the largely

unchecked circulation of extremist content, frequently amplified by bots and automated networks (Uyheng et al., 2022). Opaque algorithmic systems prioritise emotive material, aligning with affective strategies employed by far-right communicators (Lim, 2020, Woods & Hahner, 2020). This results in a feedback loop wherein provocative content is rewarded with increased visibility, facilitating ideological dissemination.

Far-right groups capitalise on social media's design by producing content optimised for engagement, while platform incentive structures further elevate their messages. This dynamic is evident in TikTok: Ozduzen, Ferenczi, and Holmes (2023) show that the platform's fast-paced, memetic style reduces cognitive resistance and heightens emotional immediacy, enabling far-right content to spread. Munger and Li (2025) demonstrate that TikTok-style "edits" can increase the perceived legitimacy and attractiveness of political figures even when ideological cues remain implicit. These examples illustrate how far-right actors strategically tailor their output to the structural affordances of contemporary platforms, creating dynamic, ambiguous ecosystems of affect within which ideological content circulates fluidly.

Building on Ahmed's (2004) concept of *affective economies*, emotions are understood here as circulating forces that acquire political value through repetition and attachment to signs, bodies, and discourses. In algorithmically curated environments, these circulations give rise to what we term *affective–discursive ecologies*, in which feeling, ideology, and platform logics intertwine through everyday participation. Within such ecologies, meaning is produced less through explicit political argumentation than through affective resonance, stylistic proximity, and repeated exposure, allowing ostensibly non-political or ambiguous content to become politicised in its reception.

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To account for how participation operates within these environments, the analysis draws on complementary conceptual lenses. De Vries's (2022) notion of the *collective avatar* highlights how users and platforms co-produce shared repertoires of affect and performance, enabling ideological tendencies to be reproduced even without explicit identification or intent. Similarly, Petersen and Johansen's (2025) concept of *hybridised prefatory extremism spaces* captures how conspiracy cues, grievances, extremist narratives, and pop-cultural references intersect within loosely structured online arenas. When framed through humour or positive affect, such spaces can function as soft entry points into radical milieus. Together, these concepts illuminate how affect, participation, and platform affordances generate conditions in which far-right ideas become ambient, familiar, and attractive within networked media environments.

Research Questions

Building on the preceding theoretical frameworks, this study examines how affective-discursive dynamics manifest within multimodal far-right communication on Instagram Reels. It focuses on the role of positively valenced affect, e.g., humour, nostalgia, pride, in softening, aestheticising, or normalising far-right aligned content. The affective and stylistic strategies specific to far-right short-form video formats remain underexplored. This study investigates how such cues operate within platform-specific cultures of participation,

and how algorithmic and user-generated dynamics sustain the visibility of far-right messaging.

The analysis is guided by the following questions:

RQ1. How do far-right and adjacent Instagram Reels mobilise humour, irony, and positively valenced affect to ideological content appealing?

RQ2. How do algorithmic recommendation systems, unaffiliated creators, and ostensibly apolitical content **appear to** contribute to the wider circulation and ambient visibility of far-right discourse on Instagram?

Methodological Approach

Following Kress's (2010) social semiotic approach and multimodal analyses of short-form video (Hakoköngäs et al., 2020, Han, 2024; Grzenkowicz & Wildfeuer, 2025), this study employed multimodal discourse analysis (MDA) to examine how far-right ideological and affective cues are encoded within Instagram Reels. MDA enables systematic attention to the interplay of modes and to how their orchestration produces meaning within digital environments. The analysis focuses on how combinations of imagery, audio, caption, and editing rhythm construct affective alignment, group identity, and ideological legitimacy.

Given the centrality of aesthetic and symbolic representation in this media form, the examination was furthered through iconographic and iconological methods (Müller, 2011) to identify coded symbols embedded in Reels. The iconographic dimension involved identifying

motifs and symbols associated with far-right visual cultures. Building on domain knowledge of far-right semiotics, this enabled systematic categorisation of visual elements across the dataset. The iconological dimension examined how these motifs function within broader ideological and affective frameworks. This approach allowed for contextually grounded interpretations of multimodal far-right communication in line with established visual research methodologies.

Instagram was selected due to its algorithmically-curated interface, popularity among younger users, and anecdotal evidence suggesting its importance in circulating extreme content. Constraints on automated data extraction favour a qualitative, close-reading methodology, aligned with the interpretive strengths of MDA and ideal for decoding semiotic nuance, irony, and affective subtext.

While RQ2 engages with algorithmic recommendation, this study does not seek to explain the technical functioning of Instagram's recommender system or to model causal radicalisation processes. Instead, it examines experiential outputs, patterns of content proximity, clustering, and contextual politicisation as they appear within curated feeds. RQ2 is therefore addressed descriptively and interpretively, rather than causally.

Data Collection

Data were collected using a digital ethnographic approach designed to approximate how users encounter content within Instagram's algorithmic environment. Two researcher-created

Instagram profiles were developed and interacted with curated content over time, exposing them to increasingly extreme material. This staged exposure simulated processes of algorithmically intensified exposure and allowed for ecological validity in sampling.

The initial “seed” Reels were identified through hashtag and keyword searches (e.g., *#remigration*, *#nationalist*, *#rightwing*), which led to far-right influencers and affiliated accounts across the Anglophone digital sphere, with notable concentrations in the United Kingdom, United States, Australia, and Canada, alongside posts originating from or connected to various European countries. This distribution reflects the transnational circulation of far-right narratives within a shared media ecology, in which symbols, memes, and ideological cues move fluidly across regional contexts. Several thematically related posts had already appeared in one researcher’s personal Instagram feed, likely due to algorithmic profiling based on age and gender, providing additional entry points for sampling. These materials formed the basis from which the researcher accounts began interacting with (viewing and saving) politically aligned content.

Each engagement prompted Instagram’s recommendation algorithm to surface additional related content, generating a recursive, self-reinforcing process in which continued interaction increased both the volume and extremity of far-right or adjacent material encountered. This method reflects the experiential reality of platform use, where engagement directly shapes subsequent exposure and contributes to the algorithmic amplification of ideologically charged content. It aligns with Christin’s (2020) notion of *algorithmic ethnography*, a qualitative approach attentive to how recommendation systems mediate meaning-making and participation within dynamic, data-driven media environments.

Accounts and Reels were classified as far-right aligned through triangulated indicators drawn from prior scholarship and policy analyses (e.g., Leidig, 2021; NCTV, 2024; Woods & Hahner, 2020). Criteria included: (1) explicit ideological markers, such as fascist symbols, historical revisionism, or white-identitarian language; (2) recurrent circulation of recognisably far-right or conspiratorial narratives (e.g., “great replacement,” anti-feminist, or ethnonationalist frames); and (3) thematic convergence with documented far-right communication repertoires, even where explicit political intent was ambiguous. This approach conceptualises ideological alignment as a continuum, capturing both overt and adjacent forms of extremist discourse.

Reels were included based on thematic relevance and a minimum engagement threshold (>400 likes or >100 comments), ensuring that the analysis centred on content with demonstrable circulation and visibility. Most selected Reels far exceeded these metrics. To reduce subjectivity in inclusion and coding, a subset was reviewed by a secondary coder to assess interpretive consistency. Coding disagreements were addressed through collaborative discussion, refining the codebook and supporting analytical rigour while acknowledging the inherent ambiguity of multimodal and affective content.

Data collection occurred between February and November 2025 through repeated observation sessions of several hours per week. Sampling continued until thematic saturation was reached, that is, when newly encountered Reels consistently reproduced previously coded themes, motifs, or affective patterns. By this stage, nearly all algorithmically surfaced content on the researcher accounts contained far-right or thematically adjacent material. This endpoint balances analytical completeness with the recognition that recommendation systems evolve

and cannot be fully captured. Saturation is therefore necessarily provisional in a dynamic digital environment, where far-right and adjacent aesthetic forms shift rapidly in response to real-world events, subcultural developments, and changing platform affordances. The dataset should thus be understood as a temporal snapshot of the affective and rhetorical evolution of contemporary far-right communication.

A total of 2,603 Instagram Reels were collected and archived for analysis. All data were securely stored and coded in NVivo, with layered structures enabling detailed cross-modal examination. This methodological design suits recommendation-driven environments in which content visibility hinges on engagement and algorithmic modulation rather than topic or chronology. By tracing recursive loops of recommendation and interaction, it illustrates how ideological material circulates through personalised pathways rather than fixed networks. Algorithmic ethnography thus provides ecological validity by showing how far-right narratives emerge, evolve, and propagate within the everyday infrastructures of platform curation. It is important to note, however, that algorithmic ethnography does not grant direct insight into the technical workings of recommendation systems. Instead, it captures their experiential outputs as they appear to specific user profiles over time. Accordingly, interpretations of algorithmic dynamics in this study are inferential and based solely on observed patterns of content exposure.

Data collection was conducted within Western Europe, with researchers moving between Belgium, France, and the UK, and initial hashtag search results and recommendations may therefore reflect regionally specific patterns of content visibility and circulation.

Coding and Analysis

To translate multimodal theory into analytical practice, each Reel was treated as the primary unit of analysis and coded at three levels (visual, sonic, and textual) prior to interpretive integration. Multiple codes could be applied to a single Reel to capture overlapping themes, affective registers, and stylistic features. This ensured that meaning was inferred from the orchestration of modes, consistent with the social-semiotic premise that multimodal meaning emerges from patterned combinations rather than isolated elements.

A structured codebook was developed through a combined deductive–inductive process, drawing on multimodal discourse analysis and policy-oriented classifications of far-right online rhetoric. Deductive codes captured thematic content, ideological markers, rhetorical and affective strategies, and multimodal features associated with far-right digital communication. Inductive codes emerged through iterative close reading, with attention to platform-specific aesthetic, sonic, and rhythmic affordances (Han, 2024) and to iconographic and iconological dimensions (Müller, 2011). Ambiguous or borderline cases were discussed collaboratively and coded conservatively, prioritising observable semiotic patterns over inferred intent. The final codebook comprises four code families, refined through coder discussion and memo-writing. A detailed version of the codebook, including full theoretical grounding and references, is provided in the online supplementary material.

1. Thematic and Ideological Codes capture narratives, tropes, and political framings expressed within a Reel. These codes were informed by prior analyses of far-right digital discourse and meme culture (e.g., DeCook, 2018; Hakoköngäs et al., 2020; McSwiney et al., 2021), alongside recent policy-oriented classifications of extremist rhetoric (NCTV, 2024).

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2. Rhetorical and Affective Strategy Codes capture how a Reel persuades, including tone, emotional appeal, and softening mechanisms. These draw on scholarship on affect in extremist communication and mainstreaming dynamics (e.g., DeVries et al., 2021; Frischlich, 2021; Rothut et al., 2024).

3. Multimodal and Platform-Native Codes capture how meaning is constructed across visual, sonic, textual, and rhythmic modes, informed by multimodal analysis frameworks (Kress, 2010; Han, 2024).

4. Meme Format / Trend Codes identify recurring platform-native genres and stylistic templates characteristic of short-form video environments.

The **full codebook** is available at https://docs.google.com/document/d/1MHuY2HP1Cjo2W89okeTcik55spnOzinTGkIV_B_FP24/view?usp=sharing

Where relevant, comment sections were consulted to contextualise affective or ideological ambiguity. While the study does not conduct a systematic audience analysis, user comments were examined where they aided interpretation of a Reel's affective or ideological tone or meaning. In cases of ambiguity, comments provided contextual cues that informed interpretive coding without being treated as data on audience reception per se. The analysis identifies communicative patterns that facilitate ideological normalisation but does not infer the strategic intent of producers or the effects on audiences. These patterns are interpreted as discursive affordances rather than deliberate persuasion strategies or audience responses.

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Ethical Considerations

All data analysed in this study were publicly accessible at the time of collection. No attempts were made to contact content producers or audiences, and engagement was limited to minimal interaction within the platform, in line with institutional and disciplinary guidelines for researching potentially harmful online material (Association of Internet Researchers, 2025).

Given the sensitivity of the dataset, steps were taken to minimise harm and avoid inadvertent amplification. Screenshots and figures were anonymised where accounts were not public-facing, and visual examples are included only where analytically indispensable. These practices are informed by a growing body of scholarship on the ethics of researching the far right, which emphasises the tension between critical scrutiny and risks of amplification or normalisation (Brown, 2024; Vaughan et al., 2024). Accordingly, the study adopts an ethics of *talking about* rather than *with* far-right actors, prioritising analytical distance, contextualisation, and harm minimisation. The analysis further acknowledges the ethical challenges of examining “soft” or affectively appealing forms of extremist communication and incorporates reflexive attention to the psychological impacts of sustained exposure, drawing on recommended risk-mitigation practices (Vaughan, 2025).

This study was conducted under ethical clearance from KU Leuven. All data are securely stored in ManGO, the university’s GDPR-compliant research repository, and can be made available for verification upon reasonable request.

Findings

Typology of Affective-Discursive Strategies in Far-Right Instagram

The analysis identifies a recurring set of affective–discursive modalities through which far-right and adjacent content is rendered resonant and shareable across accounts, formats, and degrees of ideological explicitness. These modalities illustrate how multimodal cues combine to produce softening or mobilisation effects, supporting the concept of an affective–discursive ecology in which ideology and emotion are co-produced through platform logics and user participation. While far-right media environments are often associated with negatively valenced emotions such as fear or resentment, this analysis foregrounds the role of positive and ambivalent affects, including humour and sentimentality. Reels embed exclusionary narratives within familiar affective and cultural forms, allowing ideology to circulate through modes of emotional identification and engagement.

Three recurrent, overlapping affective-discursive modalities were identified:

1. **Humorous, ironic, and meta-reflexive content**, frames ideological extremity as playful, entertaining, or self-aware transgression;

2. **Wholesome and nostalgic aestheticisation**, softens exclusionary or revisionist messages through sentimental and visually soothing imagery

3. **Inspirational, glorifying, and aspirational aestheticisation**, frames ideological alignment as awakening, purpose, or collective renewal.

Although analytically distinct, these modalities frequently overlap, with individual Reels combining multiple affective elements such as humour and nostalgia. This hybridity is central to their communicative efficacy, allowing ideological messages to circulate with deniability and broad appeal.

Affective-Discursive Ecologies of the Online Far Right

The curated feeds revealed an affective–discursive ecology in which far-right and adjacent content clustered through algorithmic recommendation and user interaction. As research accounts engaged with posts, exposure to affectively and thematically aligned material intensified, producing feeds dense with far-right symbols, references, and stylistic cues. Within this ecology, content ranged from overt neo-Nazi and race-science material to humorous, ambiguous allusions, circulating across positive and negative affective registers. This terrain was co-produced by ideological actors, platform infrastructures, and unaffiliated or semi-aligned users whose engagement, whether driven by curiosity, entertainment, or identification, could inadvertently contribute to the circulation of far-right discourse.

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The resultant affective-discursive ecology is sustained through feedback loops wherein platform and algorithmic logics, engagement-maximisation imperatives, and inconsistent moderation elevate strongly-affective content. Within this system, semi-relevant or reframed material is imbued with meanings that render it supportive or complementary to explicitly far-right content. This dynamic is exemplified in the circulation of historical and military content, like World War II documentary footage, which, when algorithmically presented alongside explicitly neo-Nazi material, is imbued with ideological meaning. Another illustration of this process is the algorithmic surfacing of content from creators unaffiliated with the far right, often members of minority communities or queer individuals. These posts frequently appear because far-right users engage with them through ridicule or outrage. Although underlying mechanisms remain opaque, recommendation systems clearly prioritise strong reaction, folding benign or progressive content into far-right viewing circuits. Such material becomes a focal point for racialised derision and dehumanisation. This algorithmically mediated proximity reinforces the antagonistic posture of far-right online identity, one defined through disidentification and hostile affect, alongside positive affirmation.

Beyond platform-level dynamics, far-right communicators shape the emotional texture of content circulating within these systems, drawing on a repertoire of affective registers to broaden appeal. These tactics align with several of Rothut et al.'s (2024) mainstreaming factors, including humorous communication, affectively charged visuals, and targeted appeals.

Humour, Irony, and Self-Reflexive Meta Content

While rage- or fear-inducing content was widespread, positively-valenced affect, like humour and relatability, performed a more subtle function. These modes allow uncommitted or ambivalent users to disavow seriousness while still amplifying extremist narratives. Humour renders exclusionary messages playful, socially acceptable, and shareable, facilitating acculturation and enabling the soft propagation of ideology.

Outrage-based humour, expressed through countercultural signalling, plays a central role in this process. The semi-ironic popularity of Kanye West's *Heil Hitler* track, often dubbed the "Instagram anthem", illustrates how ironic humour overlaps with explicit far-right signifiers. Such engagement blurs mockery and complicity while drawing mainstream attention, and potential cultural legitimisation, to marginal discourses. Within this ecology, irony operates as an affective mode of participation, enabling the casual and uncritical circulation of extremist content.

On the "radicalised" accounts observed in this study, World War II and Nazi-themed content appeared across a spectrum of tones and intentions. Explicitly humorous or ironic posts, such as fascist-themed memes or Holocaust jokes, circulated alongside ostensibly neutral material, including archival footage or trivia about fascist figures in an educational register. These genres often appeared adjacent to overt propaganda, content lamenting the defeat of Nazism, denying the Holocaust, or portraying Hitler affectionately. This proximity fused satire and sincerity, creating an environment in which extremist narratives became ambiently familiar within everyday media streams, potentially normalising their presence. This process was distinctly multimodal: for example, humorous but ambiguously framed reels incorporating

snippets of translated Hitler speeches, or AI-generated audio of Hitler’s voice singing pop songs, functioned as subcultural dog whistles recognisable to those embedded in far-right meta-communities. The sheer volume of Hitler- and fascism-referencing content played a normalising role, with, for instance, a video explaining “why the German airforce was so effective” reinforcing, through proximity and cross-modal cues, the messaging in a meme portraying “the Austrian painter” as an inspirational leader.

This tonal convergence was further reinforced by the algorithmic clustering of racially insensitive “edgy” humour, often originating outside far-right circles, with overtly extremist material. Jokes depicting Black men as unreliable fathers or Jewish people as money obsessed appeared alongside “great replacement” and white-supremacist narratives. This resulted in a feed where content of widely varying extremity, yet thematic alignment, coexisted (from ostensibly neutral posts and mildly racist humorous material to explicit neo-Nazi propaganda). Within this configuration, humour and irony rearticulate extremism as spectacle, allowing users to perform transgression, signal in-group belonging, and circulate ideological content playfully. Humor and irony reduce the social distance to extremist themes and facilitate circulation

Some examples rely on meta-ironic performance, openly acknowledging their own propagandistic quality or exaggerating extremity to the point of absurdity. Such Reels describe themselves as “propaganda,” joke about being “radicalised,” or enact extremist tropes with self-deprecating humour. This reflexive stance pre-empts critique by recasting ideological commitment as culturally fluent play, positioning extremist participation as insider wit and inviting viewers to engage on those terms. This meta-ironic style is not unique

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to far-right accounts; similar exaggerated, self-referential performances circulate in online left-leaning spaces, where irony likewise functions as a marker of subcultural identity. These performances often intersect with loosely framed conspiracy motifs, vague, humorous gestures toward shadowy elites or hidden control, which can include euphemistic antisemitic references without explicit ideological declaration. This cross-ideological uptake aligns with Petersen and Johansen's (2025) notion of hybridised prefatory extremism spaces, where irony-driven, culturally savvy performances blur ideological boundaries and create low-barrier entry points into extremist milieus.

This self-aware humour contributes to a meta-community sustained through shared irony and coded references, “Vril edits,” jokes about being watched by the “feds” or having a Mossad agent assigned as a girlfriend, among ironic racist tropes that function as markers of in-group literacy. Ambiguity is central: the same content may read as satire to casual viewers and affirmation to committed adherents. Meta-irony is often non-specific, centering on generic jokes about “racism” framed hyperbolically as “antidepressant” or “special skill.” This creates an additional discursive layer of broadly appealing, edgy humour that appears not universally offensive, yet is algorithmically clustered with, and can direct users towards, explicitly targeted racist or far-right content. Through irony and self-parody, creators reproduce extremism as an appealing participatory subculture operating across multiple affective and ideological registers.

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Figure 1. Screenshots of Instagram Reels deploying humorous, ironic, or meta-reflexive references to Nazi Germany and Adolf Hitler. These examples illustrate the Humour, Irony, and Self-Reflexive Meta Content mode, wherein extremist motifs are reframed as playful, transgressive jokes. Comedic, “edgy” content appears algorithmically clustered with explicitly racist material, demonstrating how ironic humour can serve as a low-threshold entry point into more extreme positions.

Figure 2. Screenshots of Instagram Reels employing self-reflexive humour, jokingly referencing the creator's or sharer's political extremity or racism. These examples illustrate the Humour, Irony, and Self-Reflexive Meta Content mode, in which users frame extremist postures as playful self-parody, using ironic meta-commentary to disavow seriousness while circulating far-right cues.

Wholesome and Nostalgic aestheticisation

This affective-discursive modality softens extremist messaging through *wholesomeness*, *sentimental warmth*, and *nostalgic idealism*, cultivating emotional uplift and comfort. The joyous everyday becomes a vehicle for ideology, with idyllic scenes used to evoke a sense of

belonging implicitly tied to exclusionary ethnonationalist imaginaries. In line with Rothut et al. (2024), these strategies depend on affective appeal, rendering far-right worldviews relatable, endearing, and, as often explicitly stated, “worth fighting for.”

Aesthetic devices are central to this softening. Far-right content often pairs extremist references with tranquil imagery, alpine landscapes, hazy morning light, mid-century family scenes, or romanticised rural life, producing gentle emotional registers that elicit comfort and nostalgia. These motifs evoke simplicity, goodness, and “natural order,” accompanied by neo-Nazi–inflected captions such as “life if the Austrian painter had succeeded.” Such stylised utopias equate beauty and social harmony with racial “purity,” naturalising and sentimentalising exclusionary worldviews. As Hakoköngäs et al. (2020) observe, nostalgic imagery embeds civilisational hierarchies within reassuring, familiar scenes. These visuals are frequently paired with sentimental or nostalgic music, from the Nazi-associated *Erika* to slowed, lullaby-like edits of contemporary songs, creating soothing soundscapes that further disarm audiences and ease circulation. In this mode, alignment is framed not as militancy but an embrace of harmony, belonging, or a lost ideal.

A notable subset of this content involves affectively softening portrayals of far-right historical figures, particularly Adolf Hitler. Reels depict him smiling, petting his dog, interacting gently with children or nuns, paired with warm filters and soft music. These humanising portrayals evoke empathy and disarming familiarity, reframing a reviled figure as benign, or misunderstood. As Munger and Li (2025) highlight in relation to stylised political video edits, emotionally heightened aesthetics can foster identification with public figures; here, the effect is to rehabilitate extremist icons through sentimental charm. Coded subcultural euphemisms,

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“the Austrian painter,” “Uncle H”, underpin this mode, reframing Hitler in an affectionate idiom that operates as an ironic workaround to platform moderation, and an aesthetic gesture.

Across the dataset, this wholesome-nostalgic mode creates an ambient ideological environment in which far-right narratives appear wholesome and safe. Through gentle positive visual and sonic aesthetics, these Reels transmute exclusionary, violent ideas into expressions of peaceful cultural pride and innocence. The result is a mechanism of ideological softening, making far-right content easier to accept and share.

Figure 3. A collage of Instagram Reels combining elements of the Humour, Irony, and Self-Reflexive Meta Content, and Wholesome and Nostalgic Aestheticisation modes. Posts humanise Adolf Hitler through sentimental imagery, or invoke Nazi references playfully.

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Merging irony, humour, and softness, these Reels contribute to the affective softening of extremist motifs.

Figure 4. Screenshot of an Instagram Reel pairing idyllic nature footage with references glorifying Hitler and lamenting Germany’s defeat in World War II. This example illustrates the Wholesome and Nostalgic Aestheticisation mode, in which pastoral, serene imagery is used to soften explicit extremist messaging, reframing far-right ideology through visual, emotional cues.

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Figure 5. Screenshot of an Instagram Reel showing a woman in traditional dress in an alpine landscape, holding a sticker with an idealised feminine figure and the term “REMIGRATION.” This example illustrates the Wholesome and Nostalgic Aestheticisation mode, where pastoral lifestyle imagery is used to make exclusionary ideology appear gentle and culturally familiar.

Inspirational, Glorifying, and Aspirational aestheticisation

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A third affective register centres on mobilisation through rousing, motivational, martial affect. This content evokes glory, awakening, pride, and ecstatic belonging by instrumentalising aesthetics of heroic struggle, historical destiny, civilisational exaltation, and idealised racial embodiment. Visually and sonically, it draws on imagery of martial valour, imperial nostalgia, and mythic grandeur, set to swelling orchestral scores or emotive heavy soundtracks that frame commitment to far-right ideals as exciting, a moment of revelation or righteous ascent. The overall register is triumphant, cultivating pride and an epic sense of purpose.

Central to this aesthetic are idealised gender constructs. Figures are depicted in perfected or hyper-stylised forms, muscular male bodies framed as embodiments of strength, discipline, and warriorhood; slender, ethereal, classically-beautiful white women as symbols of purity, heritage, and civilisational continuity. These visual tropes naturalise exclusionary racial logics through aestheticisation, inviting viewers to feel the beauty, power, and “rightness” of these forms and align ideology with sensory pleasure and aspiration. Historical imagery intensifies this affective pull. Reels often feature montage sequences of classical statuary, medieval knights, imperial architecture, and colonial iconography, filtered through cinematic colour grading. Such content recasts far-right ideology as the defence of a noble civilisational lineage. Martial imagery, armour, battle scenes, regimental marches, intensifies this sense of heroic continuity.

As with other affective modes, these Reels veil explicit ideology beneath aesthetic spectacle, while retaining potent emotional impact. Immersing viewers in atmospheres of triumph fosters an embodied, aspirational identification with extremist imaginaries. Far-right ideology is experienced as a call to action grounded in glory, destiny, and civilisational pride.

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Figure 6. A collage of Instagram Reels demonstrating the Inspirational, Glorifying, and Aspirational Aestheticisation, and the Wholesome and Nostalgic Aestheticisation modes. Examples feature martial imagery, cultural pride and civilisational “ingenuity” narratives, idealised colonial imagery, and rousing uprising themes, framing right wing ideological positions as uplifting and heroic.

A Layered Affective–Discursive Repertoire

Combined, these modes can be conceptualised as a multi-layered affective repertoire through which far-right ideology is rendered entertaining, endearing, and exhilarating, each mode

engaging distinct emotional registers while collectively contributing to the normalisation and mobilisation of extremist worldviews. Importantly, the actual dynamics through which such content circulates remain fundamentally opaque. The black-boxed nature of recommendation algorithms, platform-level non-transparency, and limited visibility into user practices preclude definitive claims about how individuals encounter, sequence, or interpret these modes. What follows, therefore, should not be read as a linear or causal model, but as an analytic heuristic for understanding the relational and mutually reinforcing qualities of a varied affective-discursive ecosystem.

The humour, irony, and self-reflexive meta mode provides a broad entry point, drawing diverse audiences through memes, playful ambiguity, and ironic distance. Humour enables plausible deniability while fostering subcultural belonging and normalising extremism through repeated, low-stakes exposure. The wholesome–nostalgic mode introduces emotional sincerity. It cultivates pride, tenderness, and a sense of civilisational loss, presenting a mythologised, peaceful, and implicitly white ideal as a threatened treasure. This mode addresses different affective needs by offering a sentimental vision of what has been lost and might be restored. The inspirational–glorifying mode builds on these affective repertoires by providing direction. It casts viewers as heroic defenders of the idyllic world evoked in nostalgic content, transforming resentment into rousing purpose. Where humour opens the door and nostalgia creates attachment, this mode frames ideological alignment as a necessary response to protect or reclaim an idealised past or future. These modes are best understood not as stages in a sequential pipeline but as interlocking currents within a broader affective

ecosystem, coexisting, interacting, and amplifying one another in ways shaped by platform affordances.

Limitations

While this study provides a typology of affective–aesthetic strategies in far-right Instagram Reels, it is constrained by its qualitative scope, the fluidity of online cultures, and the interpretive demands of multimodal analysis. Its focus on content rather than reception limits claims about producer intent or audience uptake. Future research could address these gaps through audience ethnography, longitudinal platform tracing, or computational approaches capable of mapping how affective repertoires circulate and evolve across digital publics.

A key methodological limitation concerns the purpose-driven design of the algorithmic ethnography. Researcher-created accounts primarily engaged with far-right and adjacent content to surface relevant material, a pattern that does not reflect everyday, mixed-use Instagram practices shaped by social ties, entertainment, and non-political interests. Consequently, the observed feeds likely intensified ideological density relative to typical user experiences. While this design is appropriate for analysing affective–discursive strategies (RQ1), it constrains interpretations of recommendation dynamics and radicalisation pathways (RQ2). Observations of algorithmic clustering should therefore be read as illustrative of potential exposure trajectories under sustained engagement rather than as representative or causal accounts of platform-wide processes.

A further limitation concerns the content-driven, effect-oriented classification strategy. Reels were categorised based on their thematic, stylistic, and affective alignment with far-right repertoires rather than inferred intent. As a result, some content may be motivated primarily by engagement-seeking practices such as approval farming, trend participation, or ironic provocation rather than by a coherent ideological strategy. Prioritising observable semiotic patterns, affective registers, and algorithmic proximity over intentionality may conflate strategic ideological signalling with opportunistic participation in far-right-coded repertoires. However, this ambiguity is treated not as analytical noise but as a constitutive feature of contemporary far-right communication, where deniability, irony, and affective circulation blur distinctions between conviction, performance, and optimisation. This approach limits claims about motivation while strengthening insight into how extremist meanings circulate and normalise within platformed economies of attention.

Conclusion

This study shows that far-right communication on Instagram operates through affective–discursive modes that obscure ideological extremity, enhance shareability, and cultivate emotional resonance within algorithmically mediated environments. Far-right actors and adjacent users embed exclusionary narratives within familiar cultural genres, humour, sentimentality, and heroic aestheticisation, reframing extremist worldviews through emotionally engaging and visually appealing forms.

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These findings deepen and operationalise Rothut et al.'s (2024) account of susceptibility within mainstreaming processes. The modalities identified here correspond closely to factors 7-9 of their model, showing how far-right discourse becomes aligned with platform affordances and affective styles that encourage circulation. They also extend Ahmed's (2004) theorisation of affective economies by illustrating how emotions, whether amusement, warmth, or triumph, circulate through multimodal cues and algorithmic clustering, acquiring political force through repetition, juxtaposition, and proximity within curated feeds.

By tracing these entanglements in situ, the study conceptualises far-right Instagram as an *affective-discursive ecology* in which ideology, affect, and platform logic are co-constitutive. The analysis **illustrates** how algorithmic recommendation systems **may** fold disparate content, including benign, oppositional, or humorous material, into circuits of far-right meaning, creating environments where extremism becomes ambiently familiar and normalised. Within this ecology, the three affective-discursive modalities identified: humorous, ironic, and meta-reflexive content, wholesome and nostalgic aestheticisation, inspirational, and glorifying, and aspirational aestheticisation, operate as interlocking components of a broader repertoire. Humour widens the field of participation through ambiguity and play; nostalgia deepens emotional attachment by aestheticising idealised ethnonationalist imaginaries; and glorifying, aspirational aesthetics channel this attachment into a sense of duty and civilisational purpose. Together, they form a layered structure in which extremist signifiers are entertaining, endearing, and heroic by turns, each register amplifying the others.

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This analysis complicates linear models of radicalisation by illustrating how far-right narratives gain traction through affective circulation and algorithmic proximity rather than overt ideological solicitation. It underscores the need for approaches to content moderation, platform governance, and digital literacy that attend to the emotional and aesthetic infrastructures through which extremist ideas are made resonant. Interventions focused solely on explicit or textualised extremism risk overlooking the subtler, affectively coded forms of ideological normalisation that thrive within contemporary digital cultures.

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